

Evaluation of Drought Relief Scheme in Vaijapur Tehsil

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Abstract

Drought is one of the most frequently occurring national disasters in India. A drought may last for weeks, months, or even years. Sometimes, drought conditions can continue for a decade or more in a region. Agricultural production and incomes are adversely affected by drought, and poverty is relatively high in affected areas. A drought is defined as drier than normal conditions. This means that a drought is "a moisture deficit relative to the average water availability at a given location and season". There are a number of drought relief schemes implemented by the government in drought-prone Vaijapur tehsil. In this study only two drought relief schemes adopted by the government are studied namely, 1) Fodder Camp (Chara Chhawani) 2) Providing water through government tankers. This study found that the highest number of beneficiary villages and hamlets was in Aurangabad division and the lowest in Nagpur. According to the respondents, the water shortage problem in the Marathwada region is worsening due to drought, low rainfall, lack of water storage, misuse of water etc. The Government water tanker, acquired well and borewell are the most effective solutions for providing immediate relief from water scarcity in Vaijapur tehsil. The study also found that, the main reason for attending fodder camps was the lack of water, lack of animal feed, and to prevent migration. After joining the fodder camp, livestock have shown positive effects. This includes improvement in animal health, increased milk production, and clean drinking water for animals at the fodder camp. About 30 percent respondents expressed concerns about ineffective management, lack of water, and political interference. More than 60 percent of respondents were satisfied with the participation of the fodder camp and the water provided by the government tanker. In short, day by day the water shortage problem in the Marathwada region is worsening due to low rainfall and lack of water storage.

Key words: Drought, Drought relief scheme

Introduction:

Drought is one of the most frequently occurring national disasters in India. A drought may last for weeks, months, or even years. Sometimes, drought conditions can continue for a decade or more in a region. The longer a drought lasts, the greater the harmful effects it has on people. Drought-prone areas are lagging behind in agriculture and also in overall economic growth. Agricultural production and incomes are adversely affected by drought, and poverty is relatively high in affected areas. The poor in these regions are highly vulnerable to a variety of risks due to their low incomes, high indebtedness and low human development. Drought often exerts substantial impacts on the ecosystems and agriculture of affected regions and causes harm to the local economy. Helping the poor to come out of vulnerability and poverty and integrating drought-prone areas into the mainstream of development is a serious challenge faced by policy makers.

A drought is defined as drier than normal conditions. This means that a drought is "a moisture deficit relative to the average water availability at a given location and season". According to the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), "drought is a deficiency of moisture that

results in adverse impacts on people, animals, or vegetation over a sizeable area".

There are a number of drought relief schemes implemented by the government in drought-prone Vaijapur tehsil. In this study only two drought relief schemes adopted by the government are studied namely, 1) Fodder Camp (Chara Chhawani) 2) Providing water through government tankers.

Objectives:

1. To assess the strengths and weaknesses of the drought policy.
2. To suggest a policy to reduce the effects of drought.

Research Methodology:

In the present study, primary and secondary data are used. For the purpose of this study, primary data is collected through a schedule questioner. In this study, we selected 100 farmers from 10 villages of Vaijapur tehsil in Aurangabad district. Secondary data was collected from authentic sources regarding the various drought schemes in the study area. For analysis, statistical tools such as percentage and average have been used in the present study.

Survey of Literature:

Sakeb Abdul Hakim Osmani & Pramod Hannantrao conducted a study on Drought

Management: A Case Study of Latur Drought 2016. The study determined that Latur received 25.95 cubic meters of water by rail. Each drop of that water was transported to every household in Latur by tankers in an equitable and fair manner. With the help of technology, the water distribution system became very transparent. The relief work of NGOs and CSOs was channeled precisely to avoid overlap. The war room was given access to a toll-free number, landline and Whatsapp in order to reach out to the maximum number of affected people. Rainwater harvesting campaigns raised awareness among citizens. Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) were prepared as per instructions of the Honourable Chief Secretary of the Government of Maharashtra.

Anil Kumar Roy & Indira Hirway studied the Multiple Impacts of Droughts and Assessment of Drought Policy in Major Drought Prone States in India. They found that regular droughts in desert areas and drought-prone areas of Gujarat have contributed to the general backwardness of its people. Both short-term and long-term impacts have been observed in these areas in terms of reduced household income, vulnerability and poverty. People in drought-prone areas are poor and face various kinds of vulnerability-physical and socio-economic during drought periods. High incidence of poverty and inadequate human development reveal the general backwardness of the people living in drought-prone areas in Gujarat. Agriculture development is very poor and has resulted in heavy loss of agriculture income due to frequent droughts and crop failures. This leads to severe indebtedness of the people in drought regions of the state. The

extent of indebtedness has been extremely high in this region.

According to Seema Kulkarni, drought has virtually come to stay for the fourth year in succession in Beed district. This is one of the three worst affected districts in the Marathwada region. While traveling through the critically affected taluk, one can see bullock carts transporting large plastic cans of water. Another can see tanker operators extracting water from bore wells and selling it in 2004. In the 177 villages of Ashti taluk, over 190 government tankers supply water daily, apart from 186 private tankers. Almost every water source including 25 to 30 large ponds and two minor irrigation projects has been dried up. Even the groundwater level has dropped by 300 feet.

An Overview of the Status of Water Crisis in Maharashtra:

Maharashtra can broadly be divided into 5 regions – the high rainfall Konkan, the drought prone Marathawada, the sugar rich Western Maharashtra, the cotton growing black soil region Vidarbha and Northern Maharashtra. Subsequent years of drought led Maharashtra to become one of the states facing alarming water scarcity. In 2019, the state government had deployed the highest number of water tankers around the most arid regions of the state. The government had also taken up the Jalyukt Shivar Abhiyan, hoping to combat the drought situation. However, 40 per cent of the state still faces water shortage issues. Total 22910 villages and 12098 hamlets in Total 27 districts of Maharashtra state provided drinking water through Government tanker, acquire of borewell, acquire of private well, temporary supplementary tab water supply during October 2015 to July 2016.

Table No 1
Division wise status of Water crisis in Maharashtra

Remedies / Work	Number of Beneficiary Villages and Hamlets							Expenditure (Rs. Lakh)
	Division							
	Kokan	Nashik	Pune	Aurangabad	Amravati	Nagpur	Total	
Water supply through government tanker	1087	2566	3369	5133	419	37	12614	31517
New borewell	744	1318	585	1774	673	636	5730	3508
Acquire of borewell	0	0	308	4846	192	0	5346	4131
Repairing of borewell	8	7	1377	993	415	230	3030	286
Acquire of Private well	0	525	271	2515	1609	279	5199	3083
Repairing of Tab Water supply	119	48	178	732	691	357	2125	6194

Well Repairing	81	0	212	70	13	73	449	159
Temporary Supplementary Tab water supply	10	112	9	190	181	11	513	2104
Construction of well	0	0	0	2	0	0	2	25
Total	2052 (5.86)	4576 (13.07)	6309 (18.02)	16255 (46.43)	4193 (11.98)	1623 (4.64)	35008 (100.00)	51007

Note: figure in bracket shows the percentage to total
Source: Economic Survey of Maharashtra-2016-17.
 Table no 1 shows that the highest number of beneficiary villages and hamlets (46.43 percent) was in Aurangabad division and the lowest in Nagpur (4.64 percent) during October 2015 to July 2016. So, we can say that water supply through government tankers was interrupted from October 2015 to July 2016 in the Marathwada region, which affected 5133 villages and hamlets. Total

expenditure on water supply through government tankers was Rs. 31517 in Maharashtra state.

Expenditure on Water crisis Relief Programme:
 The Maharashtra Government implements the Water Crisis Relief Program every year between October and July. In 2015-16, the total expenditure on the Water Crisis Relief Programme was Rs. 459.09 core and 2016-17 Rs. 514.56 Core up to December 2016.

Table No 2
Division wise Expenditure on Water Crisis Relief Programme

Division	Expenditure (Rs. Core)	
	2015-16	2016-17
Kokan	9.25 (2.01)	9.37 (1.82)
Nashik	91.52 (19.94)	44.96 (8.74)
Pune	25.47 (5.55)	20.4 (3.96)
Aurangabad	277.65 (60.48)	326.73 (63.50)
Amravati	36.14 (7.87)	65.47 (12.72)
Nagapur	19.06 (4.15)	47.63 (9.26)
Total	459.09 (100.00)	514.56 (100.00)

Source: Economic Survey of Maharashtra-2016-17.
 Table no 2 shows that expenditure on the water crisis relief programme in Aurangabad division has been increased. In 2016-17, it increased from 277.65 crores (60.48 percent) to 326.73 crores (63.50 percent), as compared to 2015-16. In addition, Kokan division expenditure decreased from 2.01 percent to 1.82 percent during the same period. So, we can say that day by day the water shortage problem in the Marathwada region is worsening due to low rainfall, lack of water storage etc.

Drinking Water Facility and Measures for to Reduce Drinking Water Scarcity in Aurangabad district

Water scarcity in Maharashtra has been a major issue, which gets more problematic in the summer every year. The Marathwada region in particular is witnessing an intense shortage of fresh water supply. According to the Aurangabad divisional commissioner's office people have to wait another 15 days for fresh water supply. Marathwada, comprising eight districts in Maharashtra, often makes headlines due to recurring droughts. Irregular rains and shifts to cash crops have made the water situation precarious in the region.

Table No 3
Drinking Water Facility and Measures in Aurangabad district

(Base year 2015-16)

10	Tehsil									Total
	Kanna d	Soygao n	Sillo d	Phulumba ri	Aurangab ad	Khultaba d	Vaijapur	Gangapur	Phatia n	
Villages (census 2011)	209	78	127	92	173	74	165	212	184	1314
Hamlets	131	9	102	59	68	53	100	53	87	662
Shortage of drinking water villages (in base year)										
Villages	43	0	0	0	5	0	5	15	20	88
Hamlets	39	2	1	4	4	6	20	30	29	135
Shortage of drinking water villages (Master Plan)										
Villages	131	36	75	83	126	69	148	183	180	1031
Hamlets	10	1	0	0	41	0	0	0	80	132
Measures										
Tanker water supply to villages	12	0	23	43	77	8	74	79	104	420
Tanker water supply to hamlets	0	0	0	0	0	2	1	2	0	5
Total No of Tankers	10	0	34	51	101	11	112	108	129	556
Other measures	40	9	37	64	93	32	69	75	18	437
Total No of other measures	41	12	52	80	110	41	104	92	19	551

Source: District socio-economic review-2016-17.
 Table no 3 shows the drinking water facilities and measures in Aurangabad district during 2015-16. Aurangabad district has 1314 villages and 614 hamlets as per the 2011 census, out of which 1031 villages and 132 hamlets had drinking water problems in 2015-16. In Aurangabad district, 420 villages are supplied with drinking water through tankers, of which 74 are in Vaijapur tehsil. In

relation to the recurring drought, 556 government water tankers were started, 112 of which were in Vaijapur tehsil.

Causes behind Water Scarcity in Vaijapur Tehsil
 Water scarcity is a major problem in Vaijapur tehsil of Aurangabad district in the Marathwada region. One of the major reasons behind water scarcity is that its demand has increased twice that earlier as the population is growing exponentially.

Table No 4
Respondents Opinion about Water scarcity in Vaijapur Tehsil

Causes	Responses
Drought	96
Low rainfall	68
Lack of water storage capacity	42
Misuse of water	20

Source: Field survey, March 2022

Table no 4 shows the respondent's opinion about water scarcity in Vaijapur tehsil. According to the 96 percent respondent's drought is a major region behind the scarcity of water, 42 percent respondents said that lack of water storage capacity, 20 percent respondent's say misuse of water and 68 percent respondent's say low rainfall are the major regions behind the water scarcity during drought period in Vaijapur tehsil.

Respondents Opinion about Measures of to Solve Water Problem in Drought period

During the drought, all surface water resources were dry. Therefore, water supply through Government tanker, acquire of private well & borewell was the feasible and suitable solution for providing immediate short-term relief from shortage of water to the citizens of Vaijapur tehsil.

Table No 5
Measures for Solve Water Problem during Drought in Vaijapur Tehsil

Measures	Responses
Government Water Tanker	92
Public well	35
Acquire of Borewell	12
Acquire of Private Well	14
Hand pump	04

Source: Field survey, March 2022

Table no 5 shows the respondents' opinions about solving the water problem during drought in Vaijapur tehsil. 92 percent of respondents said contracting a government water tanker is the most effective solution for providing immediate relief from water scarcity; 35 respondents said public wells, 12 respondents said boreholes could be acquired; 14 respondents mentioned private wells; and 04 respondents said hand pumps were effective methods for providing water during drought in Vaijapur tehsil.

Fodder Camps:

A total of 1501 fodder camps are being run in different water scarcity-hit regions of the state in May 2019; more than half of these are located in Marathwada. As per official data, around 750 fodder camps are operational in four districts of Marathwada giving shelter to over 5.25 lakh cattle belonging to the rural population of the drought-operators are required to run the camps independently for a few weeks before the state government reimburses them.

affected areas. The maximum (603) fodder camps have been running in Beed district, providing shelter to nearly 3.73 lakh adult livestock and around 30,574 calves. Osmanabad district has nearly 90 camps giving refuge to 65,435 adult cattle and around 8,127 calves. Jalna and Aurangabad districts have 31 and 26 fodder camps in place, respectively, with around 47,259 livestock. As per official records, around 390 fodder camps could not get started in the aforesaid four districts despite getting formal approval from the state government due to technical reasons.

The amount of reimbursement per animal for fodder camp operators was Rs70 per adult animal and Rs35 per calf in March. The rates were later revised and increased to Rs90 and Rs45, respectively. This was after one month and now the reimbursement amount is Rs100 and Rs50 for adult animals and calves, respectively. Fodder camp

Reasons behind participating in fodder camp:
 Table 6 shows the reasons for participating in fodder camps. According to 69 respondents, the major reason for taking part in fodder camps is due to the lack of water. 57 respondents cited the lack of

animal fodder. 46 respondents said they participated in the process to prevent migration, and 26 respondents reported having problems with animals during the drought.

Table No 6
Reasons behind participating in fodder camps:

Reasons	Responses
Water shortage	69
Fodder shortage	57
To prevent migration	46
Animal problem	26

Source: Field survey, March 2022

Impact of participation in fodder camps on livestock:

The impact of fodder camps on livestock is shown in table no 7. Some positive effects have been observed on livestock after joining the fodder camp, according to the respondents. Fodder camp

beneficiaries express their opinions. 48 respondents said that animal health has been improved because of the fodder camp. 37 beneficiaries said milk production has increased because of the fodder camp, and 34 respondents said that clean drinking water is ensured for animals at the fodder camp.

Table No 7
Impact of participation in fodder camps on livestock

Option	Responses
Improvement in health	48
Increase in milk production	37
Ensuring clean and safe drinking water	34

Source: Field survey, March 2022

Beneficiary Opinion about the Fodder Camp

Table no 8 shows respondents' perceptions/Opinions of the fodder camps. Farmers who benefit from the fodder camp express their opinions on the camp. A total of 31 respondents stated that there was a delay

in distributing feed in the fodder camp. 33 percent said that there was a lack of transparency in their camp management. 37 fodder camp beneficiaries said that there was a lack of water, and 28 respondents said that political interference occurred.

Table No 8
Beneficiary Opinion about the Fodder Camp

Opinion	Responses
Delay in distribution feed	31
Shortage of water	37
Lack of transparency	33
Political interference	28
Saved animals from starvation	19

Source: Field survey, March 2022

Level of satisfaction about drought relief scheme

We incorporate the feedback of the beneficiaries into the drought relief scheme. According to 62 respondents, the fodder camp's participation was satisfactory, while 56 respondents were satisfied with the water provided by the government tanker.

Table No 09
Level of satisfaction about drought relief scheme

Particulars	Positive Responses
Are you satisfied about supply of Government water tanker?	56
Are you satisfied with the participation of the fodder camp?	62

Source: Field survey, March 2022

Conclusion:

This study found that the highest number of beneficiary villages and hamlets was in Aurangabad division and the lowest in Nagpur. In Aurangabad district, 420 villages are supplied with drinking water through tankers, of which 74 are in Vaijapur tehsil. In relation to the recurring drought, 556 government water tankers were started, 112 of which were in Vaijapur tehsil in 2015-16. According to the respondents, the water shortage problem in the Marathwada region is worsening due to drought, low rainfall, lack of water storage, misuse of water etc. The Government water tanker, acquired well and borewell are the most effective solutions for providing immediate relief from water scarcity in Vaijapur tehsil. The study also focuses on fodder camps. The main reason for attending fodder camps was the lack of water, lack of animal feed, and to prevent migration. After joining the fodder camp, livestock have shown positive effects. This includes improvement in animal health, increased milk production, and clean drinking water for animals at the fodder camp. About 30 percent of farmers who benefited from the fodder camp gave their opinion on the camp. They expressed concerns about ineffective management, lack of water, and political interference. More than 60 percent of respondents were satisfied with the participation of the fodder camp and the water provided by the government tanker. In short, day by day the water shortage problem in the Marathwada region is worsening due to low rainfall and lack of water storage.

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